

POSSIBILITIES OF ISLAMIC FINANCING OF HOUSING RELATED OPERATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11605290>

The mortgage market is considered a fast-growing industry sector of the global financial market, and the global mortgage lending market will reach 11,487.2 billion in 2021. was estimated in dollars and by 2031 will reach 27,509.24 billion. USD, which means it will grow by 9.5% annually from 2022 to 2031. The growing trend of the world's population is causing the demand for housing financing instruments to grow.

Currently, Islamic finance, which is growing rapidly as an alternative to conventional finance, is also able to offer mortgage products, while the demand for Islamic mortgage products is also high, just like conventional mortgages. . The Shariah Council adopted the Standard on Mortgage and its Modern Application in its 23rd meeting held in the Kingdom of Bahrain on Thursday-Saturday, 15-17 Rabi-I 1430 AH, corresponding to March 12-15, 2009 AD. This made it possible to effectively organize the practice of Islamic mortgages and increased the confidence of financial consumers in these products.

In addition to housing, food and clothing, it forms the main and important part of the basic human needs. However, it has a few features that are more important than the other two needs. First, housing costs are much larger in absolute terms than food and clothing. Second, housing is the primary vehicle; therefore, housing costs are long-term investments, so it is a property investment. Third, and arguably most important, housing is a vehicle for economic development because it creates demand for various key industries, such as steel, cement, and other building materials and fixtures.

The installment price of the property sold may be higher than its cash price. It is allowed to show the cash price together with the price paid in installments over a period of time. However, the sale is void unless the parties decide whether the sale will be immediate or paid in installments. If the sale takes place while the parties are in doubt between the spot sale and the delayed sale, the transaction is void according to Sharia.

In case of non-payment of the agreed payments, it is not permissible to collect any amount in addition to the principal amount from the debtor, regardless of whether or not a condition has been set in advance. Because such an additional amount constitutes haram riba.

A solvent debtor is prohibited from delaying payments. However, it is not allowed to specify the compensation to be paid in case of delay in the contract.

In installment sales, if the debtor delays the payment of some payments, despite having agreed to this condition at the time of concluding the contract, the seller may be ordered to pay in installments before the due date. is allowed.

After the sale, the seller has no right to retain ownership of the property sold. However, it may impose a condition requiring the buyer to put the property as a lien to cover the late payments.

An installment sale can be made at an agreed price, regardless of the seller's initial purchase price (i.e. through negotiation). Also, it is permissible to enter into an agreement to give the seller a certain profit in addition to the actual cost incurred by him, as in the case of murobaha, to sell in installments based on an agreement.

This method of financing can be used for the purchase of houses that have already been built or will be built at the cost of the financier, taking into account the preferences of the potential buyer in terms of the technical characteristics of the house. Alternatively, the financier may give the prospective buyer the right to supervise the construction of the house, and then sell the house to him through musawama or murabahah.

Financing options based on deferred sales that should be considered by governments and philanthropic organizations include building and selling homes to those in need at true cost, with no profit added, through appraisal. .

As can be seen from the above research results and figures, the demand for this type of mortgage among the population is increasing due to the fact that mortgages of Islamic banks have a low level of risk, the presence of full or partial property ownership and are a source of financing in accordance with the principles of Islamic Sharia. This in itself requires further improvement of contracts and operations related to Islamic mortgages, development of strategies to create convenience for customers. Taking into account that the mortgages offered by Islamic banks are achieving positive results as an alternative to traditional mortgage loans in providing housing to the population, it is necessary to create all conditions for the further development of Islamic mortgage practice.

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